

THE ROLE OF TECHNOLOGY IN DEVELOPING COMPENSATORY COMPETENCE IN PRIMARY SCHOOL LEARNERS

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***Abstract.** The work is devoted to the development of compensatory skills in order to teach a foreign language at a language university. Definitions of the terms "competence" and "linguistic competence" are given. The levels of foreign language proficiency are considered, including basic, intermediate and advanced levels. As the main goal of mastering a foreign language, it is proposed to consider foreign language communicative competence in all the diversity of its components, which include linguistic, sociolinguistic, discursive, compensatory and sociocultural.*

***Keywords.** Competence; compensatory competence; levels of language proficiency; components of compensatory competence; types of speech activity; teaching a foreign language.*

Introduction. Language proficiency involves the formation of two main types of competencies: linguistic, studied and described mainly by representatives of linguistics, and communicative, involving the choice and implementation of speech behavior programs depending on a person's ability to navigate the situation when communicating, the ability to classify situations depending on the topic, tasks, and communicative attitudes that arise among participants before and during conversations, as well as knowledge of a regional nature.

Main part. In the foreign methodology, the leading role in the structure of communicative competence was played by M. Svaney and M. Kanel. The researchers identified grammatical competence, discursive competence, sociolinguistic competence, and strategic competence as components of communicative competence. The latter is considered as "a set of verbal and non-

verbal communication strategies that are used to compensate for insufficient knowledge of a foreign language." At the same time, as noted by X. Brown, a special place is given to strategic competence as a "way to use language tools (strategies) in order to achieve communicative goals." Exploring the essence of communicative competence, L. Bachman define compensatory competence, in his opinion, compensatory competence is "certain human abilities to use linguistic means (language competence) and psychomotor skills in the process of communication". Education helps students keep up with developments (Şimşek et al., 2008). The primary goal of education is to equip them with the skills, knowledge, and attitudes they need to become productive members of society (Yılmaz, 2007; Amankwah, Oti-Agyen & Sam, 2017). Today, children are born into a world dominated by ever-evolving technology. Therefore, they need to know the basics of technology to use it in everyday life (Öqvist & Högström, 2018). Nelson, Palonsky, and McCarthy (2010) also maintain that students should have the technological know-how and positive attitudes towards it to become productive members of society. This requires us to reconsider the role, content, and goals of education (Bellanca & Brandt, 2010).

Conclusion. In conclusion, Speaking and writing belong to the productive type of speech activity, while listening and reading belong to the reproductive type. Reading is the semantic perception of a written text, the result of which is understanding. Writing is the process of creating a text followed by its graphic fixation. The product of this type of activity is recorded text. Listening is the semantic perception of an oral utterance. Speaking is the process of forming and formulating a thought at the moment of uttering an utterance. The product of speaking is an oral spontaneous text. Thus, on the basis of the above material, a nomenclature of compensatory skills developed through types of speech activity has been developed.

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